

MEDIA AS A LEADING TOOL IN IMPROVING THE IMAGE OF THE COUNTRY

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Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda mamlakat imijini oshirishda OAVning o'rnini xususida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, mazkur maqola mavzusiga doir ilmiy va rasmiy adabiyotlar tahlil qilinib mavjud muammo yuzasidan taklif va tavsiyalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: globalizatsiya, imij, OAV, internet, jamoatchilik fikri.

Abstract. This article talks about the role of mass media in improving the image of the country today. Also, the scientific and official literature on the topic of this article is analyzed and suggestions and recommendations are given regarding the existing problem.

Key words: globalization, image, mass media, internet, public opinion.

Introduction

Information is a means of managing a person, his actions, the activities of public organizations, public authorities, technical systems. Information communication forms the basis of the upbringing, education and formation of the individual. Information is the only means of communicating to a person the content of social and technical norms, warning him about the possible negative consequences of not following these norms. We observe current topics, events, events taking place in the world through the first media. In this regard, such principles as speed, objectivity, accuracy are of primary importance to the audience. Nowadays, the internet has become an integral part of our life as a space for obtaining information and disseminating information. The Global network, globalization has also radically changed the concept of information and media.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The XXI century is the century when the theoretical and practical creativity of information reached its peak. That is why today it is argued that the 21st century is an information age. From world experience, it is known that the development of State Information Infrastructure accelerates the development of society, changing all aspects of society and the state, including the worldview of people and the conditions for their participation in labor, social and political life. Various information technologies, automated systems and a database remain an integral part of the management of state structures, the economy and the defense of the country. Today, with further development and new directions of its own, internet journalism is characterized by its wide reach and its audience's ignorance of the limits. Internet journalism, which is considered a modern type of media, the development of the media, the expansion of its tasks, drastic changes in the field of production and technology, the complication of the relationship between journalism and society, are setting new tasks for journalists. It is now important to cultivate universal journalists who can write news at the same time, master the skills of interviewing, painting and videotaping, prepare materials for the internet. At the same time, this traditional journalistic qualification now again has to generate qualifications and skills in areas of a technical nature, such as mathematics and engineering. This is especially necessary for journalists who use the internet. Thus, convergence of different areas requires journalists to both universalize and specialize. At the same time, universalization, or rather, transprofessionalization, first of all, assumes a complete assimilation of exactly one area. Universal journalist it also means a specialist who fully occupies a certain area. It is this that makes it possible to master closely related specialties at a speed. A superficial approach, simply doing everything is not enough to carry out a professional task.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the context of media Fusion, i.e. convergence, journalistic creativity is

characterized by its versatility, rapid transmission of information based on short, facts, in accordance with modern requirements. In the context of the convergence of digital technologies, the creative activity of journalists with media and information literacy rises to the stage of quality.

Also, the universalization process has created conditions for journalists to be able to do the following:

- * creating up-to-date, social information;
- be able to analyze existing social processes in a critical way;
- the scope and extent of media exposure to social processes, in which understanding forms of information representation;
- from him in demonstrating their active civic position use and understanding creatively;
- thorough and independent decision-making on all sides;
- getting new information about the environment;
- * promote the formation of a sense of commonality;
- public debates and dialogues on current issues of the development of society supply and support;
- support continuing education throughout life;
- while ensuring its own safety and feeling social responsibility media usage;
- * formation and development of civil society and global information network application[1].

All listed above kun.uz it is manifested in journalists operating on the site. The materials given under the columns of the site “Uzbekistan News”, “World News”, “Economy news”, “society news”, “science and technology news”, “sports news” are very readable as a result of a special, out-of-the-mold approach to events taking place in our republic and abroad. A journalist operating in the Internet system is definitely different from a journalist operating in radio, television, press. An Internet journalist must carry out his activities, incorporating all the features of

the above-mentioned journalists. The skill of an Internet journalist is known to be able to evaluate news. This is considered one of the main things that are required of a journalist. The selection of news and their assessment is considered one of the most difficult fists in the daily activities of an internet journalist. This also shows the journalist's experience.

For example, “.kun.uz” journalists of the site, when assessing the news, pay attention to the information policy of this site, the social significance and relevance of the event. Given on the site, “supervisory agencies must be independent. It can be observed that the message published under the heading” about one of the problems in public administration “was read 13,804 times in 2 hours, which, of course, indicates the curiosity of the audience. Messages such as” the Muslim authority's fatwa on compliance with traffic rules has been published “have also been attracting attention from users. Another of the skill edges of an Internet journalist is his speed. If 2-3 years ago, only 50 percent of the sites operating in our Republic were not regularly updated, today an increase in the demand for quality information, an increase in sites and the struggle for the information market presupposes that sites with media status are updated every day. It was described as “.kun.uz”, “.daryo.uz”, “.gazeta.uz”, “.qalampir.uz”, we can see on the example of the sites” people's word”. Materials dedicated to the current problems of today given in them are leading to an increase in user awareness. If we observe the dynamics of acquaintance with the content of sites, then www. according to the uz portal, in one day daryo.uz with about 422,496,000 users accessing the site, the third-highest ranking “.qalampir.uz” site, with about 106,086,000 users accessing its content. These indicators also show how strongly people need information today. In fact, journalists, in accordance with their professional duties, cannot live in an information vacuum. Although the information from bloggers is not officially published by journalists, they still do not lose sight of them in their daily activities. After all, the traditional media's habit of hiding information undermines trust in them. As a result, people are forced to

turn to information sources similar to blogs. In this, the audience's confidence in professional journalists decreases, and the position of bloggers continues to increase.

As a result, the rating of traditional journalism may fall slightly. The skill of an Internet journalist is primarily to convey facts of interest to the reader in the process of convergence of journalism immediately in all respects, that is, in the form of a set of text, video and audio. To date on sites (“.kun.uz”, “.daryo.uz”, “.gazeta.uz”, “.human.uz”) together with muhbir, we can observe the activities of the photographer and operator, which, of course, we can see that the journalists operating in them are not limited to text and photo, but also deliver information to the population in the form of video and audio. The effective functioning of the information and Mass Communication Agency under the administration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the creative Association of Journalists of Uzbekistan, the National Association of electronic media, the Center for retraining journalists and other organizations is another indication that all the necessary conditions have been created for the development of the information industry. The scope of work on stimulating industry employees, encouraging new creative flights, improving professional qualifications and skills, training specialists in harmony with the demand of the time is growing. These aspects are also reflected in various competitions, creative competitions, grant projects, social programs that serve the development of our journalism. In this regard, such competitions as the Golden Pen National Award, the most active journalist of the year, the greatest, the most dear, the journalists spring, the National Festival of social media products, the waves of free land are important in increasing the activity of people of creativity in society, raising professional skills, encouraging and supporting talented people.

Great attention is also paid to the improvement of the national system of training and retraining personnel for the media. In particular, at the faculties of journalism of the National University of Uzbekistan, international journalism of the Uzbek State University of world languages, as well as at the University of

journalism and mass communications of Uzbekistan, personnel are being trained for the field and in-depth study of issues related to the peculiarities of journalism, historical progress, current state and prospects in the- work is underway to ensure the effectiveness of research and creative work and to radically improve the quality of training of highly qualified personnel for this area. Constant attention and care has been provided for the consistent development of the national media, raising it to a qualitatively new level, creating the necessary conditions for its functioning at the level of requirements of World templates, supporting and encouraging the work of creators. "The processes of globalization, which in the fierce 21st century in which we live today, have entered our lives at a sharp pace, are setting the most important, urgent tasks and requirements for the people of the media and journalists of Uzbekistan on the way to building a Democratic state, a strong civil society, which is our noble goal. For this, representatives of the media are required not only professional knowledge and skills, life experience, a sense of talent for their word, but also a High grad position, spiritual courage," the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his lectures. The high confidence of the head of state in US journalists, their comprehensive support, imposes high and honorable duties on the people of honorable professions. "It was not easy for journalists at all times. We have chosen this profession knowingly. Journalism is an area that requires struggle. We want the press and media to reach the fourth level of power. Today we are trying to have full of the same power.

When talking about the freedom, achievements of Uzbek journalism, many got used to analogy with the previous era. Such a comparison is not so correct, it seems to me. Because rather than comparing our journalism to its previous situation, "what should journalism actually be like?" should be viewed with a point of view. We don't have to thank someone for the results of our industry today. Although it itself should be so, even better. I would have told my colleagues that I would like to set big goals forward and strive to become a real fourth power. You know, democracy is also viewed as the first authority in relation to the press and

media in much more developed countries. This is seen in the power of journalism. Therefore, in strong countries, strong journalism has proven itself as one of the main factors of sustainable development. Uzbek journalism should also take such a field. For this, transparency is primarily important in the development of society, the economy. You know why exactly June 27 is celebrated as the day of the press and media staff. Because on this day, our first national publication “progressive” began to be published. As we celebrate this day as a holiday, let's learn courage, courage from the people who laid the foundation of our National Press in those difficult situations of colonial times, take a soul from them. They lived with the grief of the nation.” “. Rost24.uz “site editor-in-chief Anora Sadigova, in an interview with her newspaper” Hurriyat " for the issue of June 27, 2021, described her views on achievements and shortcomings in journalism. The term information (information) is derived from the Latin word “information”, meaning to provide information, to explain [2]. From time immemorial, it was understood to exchange information between people through the means of oral, written and other methods. A broad, comprehensive explanation of the concept of” informasia " is given by cybernetics. Its founder, Nobert Wiener, writes:”Informationism is explained by the process of our adaptation to the essence of information from this external world and the adaptation of our own feelings " [3]. On the second hand, the concept of” Informationism “is also used to mean” information, that is, the transmission of information and its publicity". Information is a kind of phenomenon in the life of a person and society. On the one hand, information is a means of collecting knowledge about the world around us, providing an opportunity to adapt to the conditions of existence of Man and society, on the basis of which man and society choose the direction of action that is right for the purposes of satisfying their needs and realizing their interests.

For example, the information” it's raining down the street " helps to decide whether it is necessary to get an umbrella for a person who is riding for a walk.

On the other hand, information is a means of managing a person, his

actions, the activities of public organizations, public authorities, technical systems. Information communication forms the basis of the upbringing, education and formation of the individual. Information is the only means of communicating to a person the content of social and technical norms, warning him about the possible negative consequences of not following these norms. Today, people cannot imagine their daily life without information or news. In the modern media space, very large volumes of information are received by the audience every day. “This requires not only professional knowledge and skills from media representatives, life experience, a sense of competence for one's own word, but also a High grad position, spiritual courage.”[4] Today, in the fierce XXI century, where we live, the processes of globalization, which have been entering our lives at a sharp pace, are making urgent, urgent tasks and demands for the people of the media and journalists of Uzbekistan on the way to building a Democratic state, a strong civil society, which is our noble goal.”[5] In fact, we observe current topics, phenomena, events taking place in the world through the first media. In this regard, such principles as speed, objectivity, accuracy are of primary importance to the audience. Nowadays, the internet has become an integral part of our life as a space for obtaining information and disseminating information. The Global network, globalization has also radically changed the concept of information and media.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH. Mirziyoyev says the following points: "it should be noted separately that the Internet is getting deeper and deeper into our lives. Currently, it is noteworthy that the number of Uz-domain websites, information portals in the global network exceeds 400, most of them operate in foreign languages, a new creative generation is forming in this direction – internet journalists. Indeed, the internet has introduced new forms and styles in the activities of journalists.

Another aspect of the problem in this regard should not be overlooked above all, the internet is a source of information that is clear and ambiguous. Secondly, in

this global network, the audience acts both as a consumer of information and as a distributor of information. He concentrated a lot of resources and addresses in himself.

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